

AI Meets Toxicology¹

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Introduction. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has made significant contributions to various scientific disciplines, including Toxicology.^{1,2} Recently, the emergence of large language models with impressive text generation and contextual learning capabilities has further propelled the prominence of AI methods. Among these methods, Deep Learning³ techniques are widely used. However, despite their strengths, Deep Learning methods have inherent limitations, such as a reliance on large datasets, limited adaptability to changing domains, narrow task focus, the inability to provide guarantees beyond statistical measures, and leveraging biases in the data.⁴ In the context of chemical toxicity datasets, these challenges are particularly prominent due to the underlying selection processes that determine which chemicals are included or excluded. These and other challenges are reviewed in two articles focusing on the recent application of deep learning⁵ and, in particular, graph neural networks⁶ in toxicity prediction. The works featured in this special issue (SI) address some of these limitations through various approaches. For instance, several studies utilize traditional AI methods, such as expert systems, on smaller datasets, while others leverage additional data modalities, like bioimages, to mitigate biases and enhance method robustness. Furthermore, multi-task learning and read-across methods are employed to broaden the applicability of models and facilitate knowledge transfer between tasks. The inclusion of such diverse tasks, data types, and methodologies in this SI is a testament to the efforts made towards addressing these drawbacks and advancing the field of AI in toxicology. Below we provide a brief overview of methodological approaches and main results of the SI articles.

Approached problems and tasks. The tasks and problems spanned by the proposed methods are also highly diverse, and range from classical Quantitative Structure-Activity/Property Relationship (QSAR/QSPR) problems, such as the prediction of drug-induced liver injury (DILI),^{7,8} Ames mutagenicity^{9,10} or Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibition,¹¹ to categorization of chemicals,¹² generating transcriptomic profiles¹³ and classifying parts of regulatory documents.¹⁴ In their paper, “Transparency in modeling through careful application of OECD’s QSAR/QSPR principles via a

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curated water solubility data set” the authors¹⁵ revisited the five Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) principles for QSAR models. The discussion of these principles, which is on-going also within OECD, is addressed here with particular emphasis on the case of machine learning (ML) models. This paper smooths the path towards the increased uptake of models based on machine learning, which are sometimes criticized as being black-box. The discussion covers each individual principle, and also introduces a new one. Thus, the study highlights important requirements for the design and description of models, which need to be properly addressed by deep learning scientists if their models are to be used within the regulatory context.

Overview of used representations. Most of the presented methods perform prediction tasks on molecules (for exceptions, see paragraphs below) and, thus, have to use representations of molecules. While for data handling, the simplified molecular-input line-entry system (SMILES) representation is often used, the predominant representations of molecules for modeling are still Extended Connectivity Fingerprint (ECFP) or Morgan fingerprints.^{8–11,16–19} Several publications use graph neural networks that operate on the molecular graph.^{17,18} Aside from the chemical structure, there is a growing tendency to incorporate biological characterizations and read-outs, for example via cell morphology^{20,21} or transcriptomics.²² The utilization of diverse representations, ranging from molecular structures to biological features, enhances the predictive models showcased in this section and could improve the comprehensive understanding of toxicological properties.

Methodological overview. The methods described in this special issue cover a wide range of AI methods ranging from expert systems,^{12,16,23} over similarity measures including read-across methods,^{24–26} to classical machine learning such as Random Forests (RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)^{7–9,11,17} to Deep Learning (DL) methods^{10,11,17–21,27} including equivariant neural networks,²⁸ deep generative models¹³ and even large language models.¹⁴ In addition to models relying purely on the chemical structure there is a notable trend of bringing in additional modalities to improve or inform predictive models.^{20,21} In the following, we provide an overview of the AI approaches used in the publications contained in the SI. The methodological overview presented in this section highlights the variety of AI approaches employed in toxicology, showcasing the potential for combining different methods to enhance predictive performance and expand the scope of toxicity modeling.

Expert systems, structural alerts, read-across and similarity measures. A number of approaches can be considered as expert systems, which are a class of traditional AI methods. As an example, Chakravarti¹⁶ developed hybrid QSAR models by combining expert knowledge-based alerts and statistically mined molecular fragments, demonstrating improved predictive performance compared to models based solely on either approach, thereby enhancing the specificity and coverage of structural alerts in in-silico toxicology. Golden et al.²³ expanded a data set for skin sensitization and evaluated the performance of computational tools, which led to lower accuracies compared to previous estimates, with mispredictions and false positives highlighting the need for a more nuanced understanding of skin sensitization mechanisms beyond structural alerts and QSAR approaches. Furthermore, similarity measures and read-across methods for areas in which only small datasets are available, were developed. Read-across is a technique for estimating the toxicity of untested substances from similar chemicals (analogues), akin to the k-nearest neighbors (KNN) inference in machine learning. One of the challenges in read-across is developing suitable vector representations of chemicals based on their molecular features, physicochemical properties, and bioactivities. Yang et al.²⁶ proposed a strategy to induce hybrid vectors from chemical and bioactivity fingerprints and demonstrated its utility for predicting repeat-dose NOAEL values. They developed

a read-across approach based on chemoinformatics and machine learning that was used to estimate NOAELs for data-poor chemicals, demonstrating its effectiveness using a large set of bisphenols and their metabolites. The authors also presented an evaluation framework that could efficiently assess many substances, with the potential for further improvements using AI approaches. Banerjee & Roy²⁴ have recently introduced the quantitative read-across structure-activity relationship (q-RASAR) approach, which incorporates novel similarity-based functions as additional descriptors, resulting in enhanced predictive models compared to conventional QSAR models across multiple toxicity datasets. Lester et al.²⁵ proposed an approach that incorporates biological and toxicological features quantitatively, using fingerprint keys, to compute a similarity score for read-across predictions in toxicological safety assessment, enhancing transparency and consistency among experts and increasing regulatory acceptance. The studies discussed above all demonstrate the effectiveness of AI approaches, such as expert systems, structural alerts, and read-across methods in improving predictive performance and advancing the field of *in-silico* toxicology.

Machine learning and Deep Learning methods for QSAR. In several typical computational toxicology approaches, machine learning and deep learning methods are employed to tackle QSAR problems related to mutagenicity, organ toxicity, and drug-induced liver injury, showcasing their potential for accurate toxicity prediction. Vigaux et al.¹¹ developed machine learning classification and regression models for predicting AChE inhibition activity and IC50 values, respectively, in humans and eels, achieving high accuracy and species specificity, and created a public website, MegaAChE, for single-molecule predictions of AChE inhibition. The prediction of Ames mutagenicity is of particular concern in regulatory and pharmacological toxicology. Traditional QSAR models use molecular descriptors to predict mutagenicity, but they often fail to account for the metabolic activation of chemicals. Feeney et al.⁹ used multiple instance learning (MIL) to group chemicals and their (predicted) xenobiotic metabolites under a single mutagenicity label. The MIL models performed well in predicting Ames mutagenicity for aromatic amines, achieving results comparable to established models. Their findings suggest that MIL could supplement existing models, especially for metabolically activated xenobiotic mutagens in Ames tests with S9. Lui et al.¹⁰ have also approached Ames mutagenicity, investigating the utility of multitask deep learning and toxicology domain knowledge for task grouping in developing QSAR models. Their findings suggest that grouped multi-task neural networks, informed by mechanistic task groupings, outperform both ungrouped neural networks and single-task models, thereby showcasing the benefits of blending mechanistic and data-driven modeling for toxicological model development. Hu et al.¹⁷ have developed a graph-based deep learning model that successfully predicted eight key human organ toxicity endpoints, outperforming traditional models. The study also showed improved skin sensitization predictions through transfer learning using acute *in vivo* toxicity and Tox21 *in vitro* data. Researchers at Johnson & Johnson⁸ developed a novel method for predicting drug-induced liver injury (DILI) by using a phenotype-based annotation system, drawing on hepatotoxicity data from *in vivo* preclinical studies. Their dataset of 430 unique compounds was used to create predictive models, which yielded effective predictions for DILI labels and highlighted the impact of differences between datasets on model generalization performance. Smajić et al.¹⁹ investigated the impact of bias towards positive experimental outcomes in publicly available databases like ChEMBL on the performance of classification models in toxicology. Their findings suggest that models trained on public data tend to overpredict positives, whereas those using industry datasets predict negatives more frequently, with the study emphasizing the utility of such models in consensus modeling for predicting potential adverse events. The utilization of machine learning and deep learning techniques in QSAR modeling, as demonstrated in this section, offers valuable insights into toxicological mechanisms and enhances

predictive capabilities for various toxicity endpoints.

Deep Learning on multiple modalities and bioimaging data. Approaches that combine multiple data sources have already been adopted for their potential to improve computational methods in toxicology. Several methods of this special issue explore these multi-modal modeling approaches further. Garcia de Lomana et al.²⁰ developed machine learning models for predicting mitochondrial toxicity by incorporating curated datasets and leveraging morphological features from a Cell Painting screen, which improved the quality of predictions, while exploring the challenges and opportunities of using this approach. Herman et al.²¹ used an active learning approach combining ligand-based quantitative structure-activity relationship models and a phenotypic Cell Painting screen to improve the model performance for a mitochondrial toxicity assay, enhancing chemical diversity coverage and expanding the recognition of compounds from a broader chemical space. Bussola et al.²⁷ have presented PathologAI, a weakly-supervised deep learning framework built for classifying whole slide images in animal pathology, which was applied specifically for the prediction of necrosis in rat liver images. The ensemble model, featuring five random forest classifiers guided by features learned by convolutional neural networks, achieved up to 90% accuracy, demonstrating potential as a quick and cost-effective screening tool for preclinical applications and toxicological studies. Lejal et al.²² utilized cell painting and transcriptomic data on compounds to predict their potential for DILI. They associated cell morphological signatures with DILI chemical datasets, analyzed the mechanisms of action, identified signaling pathways related to liver toxicity, and established a hypothetical link between morphological perturbations and gene deregulation. Machine learning models based on cell morphological signatures demonstrated promising accuracy for the prediction of chemicals carrying a potential DILI risk, highlighting the value of combining high-content imaging (HCI) with transcriptomics data for comprehensive toxicity assessment in drug discovery. The integration of deep learning models with multiple modalities, as showcased in this section, provides a powerful framework for accurate toxicity prediction and offers new avenues for toxicological research, particularly in the fields of bioimaging and transcriptomics.

Special and remarkable studies. Here we highlight some special and remarkable cases, such as the application of AI language models for drug safety review and the use of generative adversarial networks for predicting transcriptomic profiles, which showcase innovative approaches that push the boundaries of toxicity assessment.

Gray et al.¹⁴ evaluated the utility of Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) models for automatic classification of free-text information into standardized sections, accelerating the review process of drug safety and efficacy. Demonstrating high accuracy in both training and testing stages, the model suggests that AI language models could enhance regulatory science approaches, facilitating the review process by effectively handling unformatted documents. Li et al.¹³ proposed a generative adversarial network (GAN) called TransOrGAN, which accurately predicts transcriptomic profiles across different organs, sexes, and age groups in rodents. This innovative approach has the potential to minimize animal usage while providing a comprehensive assessment of toxicity.

Data from chemical companies are subject to privacy and confidentiality concerns, which makes such data difficult to work with. New emerging approaches can leverage company data by using secure multiparty computation,²⁹ where calculations are performed using encrypted data, or by means of federated learning, where local models are trained in each company and only gradients are exchanged thus keeping underlying data secure as exemplified by innovative MELLODDY project.³⁰ Bassani et al.³¹ describe the experience of Roche scientists, who used an alternative

method in which local models predicted an unlabeled set, which was then used to teach the federated model, thus exploiting the idea of surrogate data sharing.³² DL can especially capitalize on such methods particularly in the toxicology field, where data are sparse, limited and frequently distributed between multiple partners.

Conclusion. This special issue on AI methods in toxicology reveals the wide-ranging applications of AI methods, including expert systems, machine learning algorithms, deep learning models, and large language models. The approaches presented here address various challenges and tasks in toxicology, highlighting the potential of AI to enhance predictive performance, overcome limitations, and pave the way for more accurate and efficient toxicity assessment in the future, while giving an overview of the requirements for such models to be used within the regulatory context.

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